

Words That Are Not Words: Digital Approaches to Magical Language and Iconography in Antiquity

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What if meaning in a text does not reside in words alone, but is generated through the structured interaction of sound, image, and pattern? This paper advances the claim that magical documents from Roman and Late Antique Egypt form a coherent system of multimodal ritual communication, in which *voces magicae*, figurative images, and signs (*charaktēres*) interact to generate meaning beyond conventional language. We argue that these elements are not marginal or opaque residues, but integral components of a form of non-linear, multimodal storytelling, and that an integrated Digital Humanities approach can adequately account for their structure and function.

The paper presents a unified framework that brings into direct methodological alignment two ongoing projects: *Names and Orality in Magic IN Antiquity (NOMINA)*, funded by the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (H.F.R.I., Grant no. FM3-25134), and a parallel project on figurative imagery in magical texts and artefacts, *TO ZŌDION: Images of Power and the Power of Images in Magic in Antiquity*. Both projects draw on the same corpus — primarily the Graeco-Egyptian magical texts — and are developed as interconnected but distinct databases, designed to enable systematic cross-modal analysis.

At the core of our approach lies a common premise: that meaning in magical texts emerges not from isolated elements, but from patterned relations across phonetic, visual, and contextual levels. The digital infrastructure is therefore designed to capture these relational dynamics, linking individual attestations — words, images, and signs — to broader ritual, structural, and cultural configurations. In this sense, the two interconnected databases do not merely aggregate material, but jointly model the implicit “narratives” of ritual practice as they unfold across multiple semiotic registers.

We begin with the *NOMINA* project, presented here in its expanded, fully functional state. The project is dedicated to the systematic study of so-called *voces magicae* — enigmatic strings of letters or “words of power” that permeate ancient formularies and so-called “activated” objects such as amulets, phylacteries, and curse tablets.¹ These forms exhibit a wide spectrum of linguistic and pseudo-linguistic features: some resemble actual words in Egyptian, Greek, or Hebrew (e.g. BAINCHŌŌŌCH, a Greek transliteration of the Demotic *bʿ n kkw*, meaning “soul of the primeval god of darkness”), others appear as isopsephistic sequences (such as ABRASAX, summing to 365) or palindromes (such as ABLANATHANALBA), while still others take the form of extended, largely non-sensical letter-strings (e.g. the IAEŌBAPHRENEMOUN-*logos*, comprising 59 letters).² Like the figurative images (see below) and *charaktēres* that frequently accompany them, these forms have long been marginalised in scholarship: visually or phonetically striking yet philologically elusive, simultaneously meaning-laden and resistant to conventional interpretation.

NOMINA addresses this gap by enabling a large-scale, systematic exploration of magical words as structured data. The platform currently organises more than 8,000 magical words and divine

¹ Nagel 2021 with further references.

² Sarischouli 2025. An older glossary of magical words is found in Brashear 1995.

names preserved in the Graeco-Egyptian magical corpus.³ These are structured through a tripartite analytical model — *Word*, *Lemma*, and *Logos* — which allows users to move between individual manuscript attestations, grouped variant forms, and longer recurring sequences. *Word* entries reproduce each attestation as it appears in the manuscript, in both original script and transcription (vocalised or not, depending on the language). *Lemma* entries gather variant spellings under a shared identifier, enabling the reconstruction of families of related forms. *Logos* entries capture extended sequences in which individual words participate, linking them through a unique reference code. This structure renders fragmentary data intelligible within broader patterns of ritual logic, phonetic play, semantic clustering, and scribal creativity.

Conceived as an open and evolving research environment, *NOMINA* is supported by a dedicated website hosting the database, project updates, bibliographies, and tools for collaborative annotation. Advanced search filters (covering original script, transliteration, date, provenance, textual and ritual context, auditory and visual effects, and paleographic features) facilitate interdisciplinary engagement by papyrologists, classicists, linguists, historians of religion, and digital humanists. Each entry is fully interoperable, linking to identifiers in the *Kyprianos Database of Ancient Ritual Texts and Objects*⁴ and in *Trismegistos*.⁵ This integration situates *NOMINA* within the broader archaeological and papyrological digital ecosystem, reducing redundancy while enabling cross-corpus comparison.

Fig. 1: The *NOMINA* website

Fig. 2: The *NOMINA* database

The dataset currently spans the first to sixth centuries CE, with planned expansion into Late Antique and early medieval traditions up to the twelfth century, enabling a diachronic investigation of how pseudo-linguistic speech circulates, transforms, and acquires new ritual functions across cultural contexts. This framework supports a set of interrelated research questions:

- (a) contextual distribution: which magical words, names and letter-strings are associated with specific ritual aims?
- (b) intercultural transmission: how such forms are borrowed, adapted, or transformed across linguistic traditions (Greek, Egyptian, Semitic)?
- (c) linguistic development: how meaningful lexical items evolve into apparently non-sensical sequences?

³ Faraone and Torallas Tovar 2022a; 2022b.

⁴ <https://www.coptic-magic.phil.uni-wuerzburg.de/index.php/manuscripts-search/>

⁵ <https://www.trismegistos.org/magic/>

(d) chronological and geographical variation: how do specific forms circulate and change across time and space?

By confronting these questions, the *NOMINA*-project seeks to reposition magical language not as a barrier to interpretation but as an active agent in ritual communication, approachable through a combination of conceptual analysis, computational techniques, and large-scale corpus organization.

These textual phenomena, however, do not operate in isolation. *Voces magicae* are frequently embedded within broader multimodal configurations in which images and signs play equally constitutive roles. The second component of our framework therefore focuses on figurative imagery — depictions of deities, demons, victims, and symbols of power — that appear alongside magical language and symbols in manuscripts and artefacts.⁶ Rather than treating these images as ancillary illustrations, we approach them as visual operators within the same semiotic system, encoding meaning through form, repetition, and spatial arrangement.

Fig. 3: Armed god Seth on a Demotic papyrus (Leiden RMO collection, AMS 75, fol. 1)

Figs 2 and 3: Magical figures surrounded by *charaktēres* on a Greek papyrus (Oslo University Library collection, P.Oslo I 1 col. ii and P.Oslo I 1 col. vii)⁷

As with magical words, these images are often fragmentary and highly variable at the level of individual attestations, yet reveal regularities when analysed at scale — above all when stereotypical groups are identified on the basis of the rituals they accompany or the *voces* and *charaktēres* interconnected with them. Their reconstruction and interpretation therefore require

⁶ Martín Hernández 2012; Gordon 2018; Martín Hernández 2022.

⁷ <https://papyrus-stories.com/2018/11/16/how-to-be-successful-in-life-fourth-century-style/> (retrieved 06.12.2025)

a systematic, comparative methodology parallel to that applied in *NOMINA*. To support this aim, we are currently developing a dedicated, structured database of figurative imagery (*TO ZŌDION*), organised according to geographic, chronological, and functional parameters, the latter defined through tags referring to such stereotypical groups. Crucially, records in *TO ZŌDION* that register images together with associated *voces* and *logoi* will be directly linked to the *NOMINA* database. In this way, the two relational databases are designed to complement one another: their interconnection will allow us to map systematically the relationships between *voces*, *logoi*, and images—relationships that are often assumed in studies of magic but have not yet been methodically formalised..

Given their inherently two-dimensional nature, the images can be normalised through schematic tracing, enabling their transformation into comparable visual data. The corpus of images from the Graeco-Egyptian magical papyri has already been processed using an automatic binarization workflow, producing standardised black-and-white renderings that minimise subjective intervention while preserving diagnostically relevant features.⁸

Although individual representations are often highly idiosyncratic, large-scale aggregation reveals recurring iconographic patterns detectable through cross-corpus comparison with both magical and contemporaneous non-magical imagery. Reconstruction and contextualisation thus depend on corpus expansion and feature extraction. Each image is therefore annotated using a controlled vocabulary of iconographic descriptors — such as posture, attributes, orientation, and relational positioning — enabling the systematic identification and comparison of visual features across the dataset. Building on this structured and annotated corpus, a second phase of the project will explore AI-assisted methods for pattern recognition and similarity detection, with the aim of identifying recurrent configurations and proposing reconstructions of partially preserved images. The recurrence of specific patterns — whether in the repetition of image types within particular rituals or in the association of *voces* with specific visual forms — can support the reliable reconstruction of underlying models, in much the same way that gaps in textual material are supplemented through recurring sequences (*logoi*). Such reconstructions, grounded in statistically significant correspondences within the dataset,⁹ contribute to modelling incomplete visual structures and substantially expand the evidential basis available for analysis.

The integration and interrelation of these two datasets constitute the central methodological aim of the paper. Words and images are linked through shared metadata fields — such as ritual function, material context, provenance, and date — creating synergies that enable the interconnected study of *voces* and images, two phenomena that, although co-present in ancient artefacts and documents, have typically been examined in isolation. This framework supports the identification of multimodal patterns, including the co-occurrence of specific *voces magicae* with particular iconographic motifs, correlations between phonetic and visual variation, and the detection of recurrent clusters of words, images, and signs associated with specific ritual operations. Methodologically, both domains converge within a shared computational, AI-assisted pipeline: pattern detection, clustering, and sequence analysis are applied to textual data, while machine-assisted comparison and reconstruction are used for visual material. This integrated approach moves beyond parallel description towards the modelling of multimodal meaning in ritual contexts.

Across both datasets, three overarching challenges emerge: distinguishing intentional variation from “noise” (whether scribal or material), classifying hybrid forms across linguistic and iconographic traditions, and deploying AI-based pattern recognition to identify recurrent

⁸ Shaus and Martin Hernandez 2022.

⁹ Numerous tools and methods are currently available; see, e.g., Ishac 2025; Tian *et al.* 2025.

structural configurations in both *voces magicae* and images. Preliminary results show that this database-driven methodology reveals consistent combinatory patterns linking words and images, thereby providing concrete evidence for the internal logic of ritual composition.

By modelling magical language and imagery as a unified system of ritual signification, this paper makes a methodological contribution to Digital Humanities. It demonstrates that fragmentary, non-standard, and non-linguistic data can be systematically analysed through integrated, relational frameworks, while also engaging with Digital Storytelling by showing how meaning emerges through non-linear, cross-media assemblages that operate beyond conventional narrative forms.

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